

Dissociation constants of acetic acid in acetone + water mixture

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The thermodynamic dissociation constants of CH₃COOH in acetone-water mixtures (8.04–87.62 wt%) have been determined pH-metrically. As expected the dissociation constants (–log K_a) increase continuously with increase in organic co-solvent. The results have been explained in terms of solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity.

In recent years, Lahiri and co-workers¹ determined the Gibbs energy of transfer of H⁺ ion from water to different binary aquo-organic mixtures based on the thermodynamic dissociation constants of 'isoelectric reactions' like

where L = 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) or 1,10-phenanthroline (phen). However, solvent effect or medium effect on *K* values is usually masked in systems containing excess of electrolytes. The determination of thermodynamic dissociation constants in dilute solutions appears to be the ideal choice to avoid solvent perturbation (structural changes of solvent due to solvation of ions, ion-association etc.) in presence of excess electrolytes. Under this condition, the 'medium effect' due to addition of co-solvent (organic) to water can be assumed to be totally reflected on *K* values.

Both bipy and phen absorb strongly in the uv-region. The absorption characteristics enabled Lahiri *et al.*² to determine their thermodynamic dissociation constants for the reaction of the type (1) spectrophotometrically. Naturally, spectrophotometric determination of the dissociation constants in aquo-organic mixtures using 10^{–5}*M* ligand appeared to be the ideal choice. However, the method requires accurate H⁺ ion values using low concentrations (=10^{–5}*M*) of acid. This is possible only with the use of suitable buffers of neutral electrolytes in these aquo-organic mixtures. CH₃COOH + CH₃COONa buffers were considered to be the best for the purpose but the system did not work obviously due to increasing p*K* values of acetic acid in binary mixtures similar to that observed by other workers³ in MeOH + water mixtures. This led us to determine the dissociation constants of acetic acid,

in acetone + water mixtures (8–87 wt% of acetone) to understand the solvent effect on the dissociation constants of acetic acid. The results are reported in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for acetic acid (HA) can be represented as

$$K = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{X}^-}}{C_{\text{HX}}} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{X}^-}}{\gamma_{\text{HX}}} \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{X}^-}}{C_{\text{HX}}} \cdot \gamma_{\pm}^2 \quad (4)$$

where γ_+ and γ_- are the ionic activity coefficients and γ_{\pm} is the mean activity coefficient of the two ions. Here γ_{HX} has been assumed to be unity.

In absence of suitable buffers, it is not possible to measure H⁺ ion activity in mixed solvents using glass-calomel electrode, rather the H⁺ ion concentration is measured. Therefore

$$\text{p}K = -\log [\text{H}^+] - \log \frac{[\text{X}^-]}{[\text{HX}]} - 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} \quad (5)$$

where [H⁺], [X[–]] and [HX] represent the equilibrium concentrations of H⁺ ion, anion (X[–]) and CH₃COOH (HX). From the difference between the experimental solution and blank solutions, [X[–]] can be determined and

$$[\text{HX}] = [\text{HX}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{X}^-] \quad (6)$$

The activity coefficients have been calculated using Davies equation⁴,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{AZ_+ Z_- \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (7)$$

A values in different mixed solvents at 298 K (denoted by *A'*) have been calculated using the relation,

$$\frac{A'}{A} = \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon'} \right)^{3/2}$$

where *A* = 0.509 (in water) and the relative permittivity or dielectric constant values (ϵ) in mixed solvents are interpolated values based on the data of Akerlof⁵.

pK values calculated are recorded in the Table 1

Table 1. pK_a and free energy of transfer data of acetic acid in different acetone-water medium

Wt % of acetone	Mole frac acetone	$1/\epsilon \times 10^2$	pK_a	ΔG_i^0 kJ mol^{-1}
8.04	0.026	1.36	4.80 (± 0.02)	27.37
16.44	0.057	1.46	5.05 (± 0.01)	28.80
25.22	0.095	1.58	5.37 (± 0.03)	30.63
34.40	0.140	1.74	5.69 (± 0.01)	32.45
44.03	0.196	1.93	6.01 (± 0.02)	34.28
54.13	0.268	2.18	6.58 (± 0.02)	37.53
64.74	0.363	2.53	7.50 (± 0.02)	42.77
75.89	0.494	3.08	8.61 (± 0.04)	49.10
87.62	0.687	3.92	10.39 (± 0.04)	59.26

The effect of organic co-solvent can be observed from the plot of pK against wt% of acetone, mole-fraction and $1/\epsilon$ values. The pK values increase continuously and the linearity suggests that electrostatic component is probably the main contributing factor. The contrasting effects of solvents for reactions of different charge types like (1) and (2) can be had from the plots of ΔpK [$pK(s) - pK(W)$] against wt% of acetone (Fig. 1). The electrostatic effect on the Gibbs energy changes is expected to be prominent in case

Fig. 1

of reaction (2) than in (1). However, the differences in energy changes also arise from non-electrostatic component resulting from solute-solvent interactions which is obviously different for CH_3COO^- and phenH^+ and CH_3COOH and phen . Bates and Robinson⁶ calculated the

non-electrostatic components for the Gibbs energy changes assuming $r_{\text{H}^+} = 0.86 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_{\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-} = 0.63 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_{\text{nitroanilinium ion}} = 1.5 \text{ \AA}$. The negative values of the non-electrostatic components are ascribed to increased basicity of the solvent mixtures. However, in view of uncertainty of the radii values, true values of the non-electrostatic component cannot be determined or uncertainty will be large.

In order to comprehend the systems better, the data should be analysed in terms of single ion values which, however, proved elusive in view of the lack of data on Gibbs energies of transfer of the neutral components. But we have

$$\Delta G_i^0(1) = \Delta G_i^0(L) + \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_i^0(L) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+) = \Delta G_i^0(1) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$$

Similarly, we have

$$\Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}) = \Delta G_i^0(2) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$$

$\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$ values have been taken from our earlier work⁷. The variations of $[\Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH})]$ and $[\Delta G_i^0(L) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)]$ appear to be similar but opposite in nature through the magnitude is higher for $[\Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH})]$. The plots of $[\Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH})]$ and $[\Delta G_i^0(L) - \Delta G_i^0(\text{LH}^+)]$ against wt% are shown in Fig. 2. The results suggest that the decrease in dielectric constant obviously favours association in case of reaction (2). Moreover, the increase in basicity is a contributing factor. These led to uniform increase of pK values

Fig. 2

for reaction (2) but not for (1). Increased molecular interactions and hydrogen bonding of CH₃COOH with CO group of acetone (determining cation-O-centre interacting capacity of acetone) favour dissolution of CH₃COOH making $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH})$ highly negative. However, decreased interaction of CH₃COO⁻ with acetone may be assumed making $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-)$ fairly positive. Though the interaction of L with acetone is probably less but solubility values of L increase, i.e. ΔG_f° is increasingly negative but $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{LH}^+)$ is increasingly positive which outweighs the contribution of $\Delta G_f^\circ(\text{L})$.

Experimental

Acetic acid, perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and succinic acid (all G.R., E. Merck) were used. Acetone (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by mixing with pure CaO (Pfizer), the mixture kept overnight and distilled after filtering through nonabsorbent cotton. The experiment was performed with the middle fraction of the solvent.

The pH-meter readings of solution containing known concentration of acetic acid, but neutralised to different extents by caustic soda solution in different volumetric flasks and the corresponding blank solutions without acetic acid were noted. The data were utilised to calculate pK values in different aquo-organic mixtures.

The pH was measured using an Orion-expandable pH-meter.

Calibration of the glass electrodes : In absence of suitable buffers in acetone + water mixtures, the glass-calomel electrode combination cannot be calibrated and hence unable to give accurate H⁺ ion activity values. The measured values give meter readings which with 'appropriate corrections' give H⁺ concentrations. The 'correction terms' in mixed solvents were obtained in the way suggested by Van Uitert and Hass⁸. The 'correction terms' $\log U_H$ in mixed solvents were obtained from the relation,

$$-\log [\text{H}^+] = B + \log U_H$$

where $-\log [\text{H}^+]$ is the stoichiometric H⁺ ion concentration of the reference solution in water [$10^{-4} \text{ M HClO}_4 = 4$] and B represents the meter-reading of 10^{-4} M HClO_4 in mixed solvents.

The Orion instrument is capable of measuring H⁺ ion concentrations upto 0.001 pH units. However, in view of liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude, the meter reading were rounded upto 0.01 units.

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